

An Overview of “Digitalization of Human Resource Management”- A Key towards Organization’s Success

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Archana, et al.

“An Overview of ‘Digitalization of Human Resource Management’- A Key towards Organization’s Success.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 66–69.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575293>

Dr. Archana

Professor PG Department, Jain College

MG. Aishwarya & R. Yashodha

1ST M.Com, Jain College

Abstract

The rapidly increasing technological development results in digitalization of the society. The aim of this paper is to get a deeper understanding of how digitalization has been introduced in the HR department. The paper illuminates to explore the use of technology driven tools in HR practices. The technology Revolution has helped the HR professionals to use this innovation in positive way. The technology impacts HR practices like recruitment, training, development, performance management and payroll management.

Keywords: Digitalization, Illuminates, Revolutions.

Introduction

The technological development has revolutionized the society to impact and change the way organizations work and to adopts to the fast-changing digital innovations. Digitalization will reduce manual work task by increasing use of technology. The e-HRM plays a crucial role as it has made the process carrier and user friendly while ensuring accuracy with precise results. Digitalization has been continuously changing the way the organization works as in the way it hires, manage and support people. HR professionals must analyze social, economic, political-legal, and technological environment opportunities to redesign HRM processes and practices that are key success factors to the organization mission and objective.

A varied number of technologies are used to facilitate the working of human resource department. The e-HRM plays a crucial role as it has made the process easier user friendly while ensuring accuracy with precise results. The digitalization has transformed the HR functioning over the decade. To have an impact, HR must develop advanced capabilities to align HR structure and services with the business needs that facilitate business growth and operational excellence. HR Transformation has led to restructuring of HR operations and working.

Digitalization in HR in Global Senario

From the above graph it can be inferred that India stands 1st place in adopting digitalization in HRM.

Digital HR is a process optimization in which social, mobile, analytics and cloud (SMAC) technologies are leveraged to make HR more efficient. In other words, it's a tectonic shift in the way Human Resource Function.

The digitalization of HR refers to increasing use of digital technologies to drive business objectives in HR. For a long time HR professionals have mostly worked in solution performing their daily administrative duties religiously. HR departments are embracing ownership of IT system to achieve automation in their process and drive business objectives.

Objectives

1. To recognize the implications of digitalization of HR functions.
2. To understand how the organization use the digital transformation and how it is directly and indirectly affects the organization success.
3. To study the challenges of digitalization in HR department.
4. To provide suggestions and recommendations to meet those challenges.

Sources of Information

The data was collected with help of secondary source

Published and unpublished information was studied to collect information. Data was also collected from the information released by government of India on related website.

Challenges Faced by the HR Department

The main goal of the Human Resource department is to provide guidance, information and to introduce best practices to address the latest key issues related to the functioning of the HR department.

Advice on strategic, policy and technical issues, and help formulate industry positions on leading HR practices;

Monitor industry Human Resource developments and trends and their implications;
Help define industry best practice and standards in Human Resources and training;
Assist in the production of HR Guidance material, training content and other publication
Advice on the need and assist in the development of industry benchmark surveys, analysis.

Technology to Overcome the Challenges

HR department is also starting to take advantage of human resources management software built on technologies such as analytics, big data, and the internet of things for functions ranging from understanding why employees are stressed, and all the issues related to employees retention, turnover, compensation, and welfare.

Digitalization to Meet the Challenges in Recruitment

Online recruitment refers to posting vacancies on the corporate web site or on job portals which easily allow the applicant to share their resume via Email, E-recruitment is the use of web based which helps to support the recruitment process.

Digitalization to Meet Challenges in Training and Development

“E learning refers to the use of internet technologies to deliver a broad way of solutions that enhance knowledge and performance. The need for more information is becoming more crucial as organizations want to be sure of effectiveness before they decide whether they should use it or not. Due to availability of online training employees can use the module to their ease and learn on their own.

Digitalization to Meet the Challenges in Performance Management

Online performance system helps the organization to conduct the whole appraisal procedure online. The online procedure helps in reducing the paper work and decreasing the time and cost of the HR department. The online appraisal procedure helps increasing productivity, relationship and core competency. The automated process of performance appraisal management organizations uses various performance management Suite System.

Digitalization to Meet the Challenges in Payroll Management

The online payroll updating has helped the organization in easy disbursement of salary to employees. Digitalization in payroll has helping the organization to move towards the new cloud computing technology. It has helped in easy managing on server with very less maintenance cost. It has helped in keeping a record of employee efficiency which helped easily providing the bonus and incentives.

Digital Transformation and Organization Success

The digitalization has helped the organization in many ways which leads to the employees’ engagement and success of the organization. The internet technology helped in automating the routine task of HR professionals replacing the cabinets. Digitalization has made the employee enterprise connectedness. Digital technology has Enable a comprehensive employee engagement which leads to the employee performance. It has helped in increased involvement of employees in organization’s HR practices and employee become savvy about the HR practices.

Indian Companies Who Have Digitalized their HR

1. Infosys

It focuses on changing the organization’s end-to-end thinking on HR, and aligning its practices, process and culture to SMACI (Social, Mobile, Analytics, Cloud and IOT(Internet of things))

2. TCS (Tata Consultancy Services)

It focuses on the digital transformations, digital software and solutions, cloud, analytics, driving exponential growth.

	TCS	Infosys
FY19 \$ Revenue	\$20.91 b	\$11.79 b
Margin	25.6%	22.8%
FY19 Net Profit	\$4.5 b	\$2.2 b
Digital Contribution	31%	34%
Headcount	424,285	228,123
Net Addition	29,287	24,016
Attrition	11.3%	20.4%
Growth Forecast FY20	Not given	7.5-9.5%
Margin Guidance	26-28%	21-23%

The above table shows 31% and 34% of net profit of TCS and Infosys respectively are transferred to digital contribution.

Conclusion

With the ongoing trend of change in technology, the organization need to be updated and adapt the change in order to survive in the organization. Digitalization has effected the whole organization either indirectly or directly. Organizations are working to reduce their cost and adapt the technology changes. Companies are trying to adapt the E-HRM practice to enhance the efficiency throughout the organization. The new technology effect the organization in building employee engagement and provide more transparency in working which help the organization in building employees loyalty leading to organization success. This study contributes to the deeper understanding as how digitalization has implications on HRM.

References

1. CapGemini Consulting
2. Fisher, C., & Sempik, A.
3. Leopold, J., & Harris, L.
4. Raja, J., Green, S. D., Leiringer, R.
5. Salman, G., Storey, J., & Billsberry, J.